

A Sustainable Supply Chain with Several Retailers and A Single Manufacturer formed in an Inventory Model with Fluctuating Transport Expenses.

M. Karthic ¹, A. Sridhar ²

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics,
Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai,

² Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics,
Government Thirumagal Mills College, Gudiyattam.
Tamilnadu, India.

Abstract - In response to consumer demand for eco-friendly products, the assembly and redesign approach known as sustainable single manufacturer multi retailer emerged. Order quantity and discrete purchasing cost reduction are additional factors that influence the manufacturer's desired minimal cost along with carbon emissions. The model is used to optimize the order quantity (lot-size) for production and rework, the amount of money spent on green initiatives and the environmental measure. The findings of the research work suggest that the profitability of the producers and retailers will grow once the environment and consumer demand for green products are taken into account. In addition, the model is illustrated with various numerical examples, with the goal of investigating the effects of model parameters according to the ideal outcomes.

Keywords - Sustainable Supply Chain; Fluctuating Transport Expenses; Several Retailer Emerged; Green Products; Single Manufacturer;

1. Introduction:

The primary goal of every company, whether it operates in the public, private, or government sectors, in today's cutthroat marketplace is to increase revenues while minimizing expenses. To survive and grow, an industrial company needs to minimize overall costs, keep cost control, and boost profitability and operational effectiveness. Ensuring client satisfaction is inventory control's primary goal. This is due to the fact that poor stock management can result in backlogs, missed sales, deficient orders, and delayed deliveries, all of which can aggravate customers. The other goal is to decrease the cost of providing a reasonable level of clientele in order to increase efficiency either now or in the future. Inventory is a crucial instrument for managing stock and cutting waste, and it is considered an integral part of the industry. The ability and mobility of raw materials, inventory for work-in-progress, and packaged items are all part of the flow of goods and services. Many strategies, such as waste reduction, packing material reduction, compliance maintenance, sourcing from sustainable suppliers, and carbon emission reduction, are used to develop sustainable supply chain management. Configuration expenses come in two flavors: variable as well as fixed. Capital expenditures like machine parts required to get the machine ready for a fresh lot are included in fixed costs. Variable expenses include things like personnel salaries and consumables required in setups that change based on the expertise level of the individuals involved.

The novel aspects of this study are as follows: (1) strengthens the theoretical underpinnings of sustainable inventory management; (2) develops an integrated SVSB-SC model; (3) offers investment, production, and cost reduction; and (4) employs mathematical modeling and solution processes to derive ideal outcomes for the total cost function. (5) To verify the efficacy of our model by numerical analysis and comparative study.

What's defined in the rest of this paper is: The relevant literature survey is described in Section (2). The notations and presumptions are constructed in Section (3). The mathematical modeling for determining the lowest setup, purchasing, and SC costs is shown in Section (4). The study's limitations and numerical results are presented in Section (5), along with some managerial insights. In Section (6), the conclusion and future plans are provided.

2. Literature Survey:

Villena, V. H., & Gioia, D. A. [1] created a supply network that is more sustainable. et al. (2020). [2] described a Prospects and challenges within the environmental supply chain from the standpoint of operations research. Povoia, da Silva, & Carvalho. et al.

(2018), Roussanaly, & Tomasgard, [3] considered the best cost and design for ship-based CO₂ transportation in the face of uncertainty and volatility. Yadav, A. S., & Swami, A., et al. (2020). [4] implemented a volume adaptable two-warehouse model that can adjust costs to account for inflation and demand fluctuations. Jones, J. et al (2019). [5] addressed the people who benefit, lose, and are shaped by changes in fuel prices. Sierra Leone et al. (2022) [6] examined a sustainable reworking model for discrete purchasing that reduces costs for a single producer and several retailers while meeting green and environmentally conscientious demand. Malleeswaran & Uthayakumar et al. (2023), [7] Incorporating service level restrictions and carbon emission fees, an extended integrated vendor-buyer supply chain model is constructed for price dependent demand and backorder price reductions. Malleeswaran, & Uthayakumar, et al (2020), [8] analyzed a consignment stock management system that reduces waste products and greenhouse gas emissions through remanufacturing, emission penalties, and promotional initiatives - all within capacity constraints. B. Malleeswaran & R.Uthayakumar et al. (2021), [9] investigated agreements for supply chain synchronization that account for demand-dependent retail prices and stock levels. Saha, S., & Goyal, S. K. et al (2015), [10] studied supply chain management for green products, a synopsis of the most recent discoveries. Srivastava, S. K. et al. (2007), [11] developed using carbon emission factors for stock selection, planned discounts, shared costing, and full repurchasing. Moon, Hazarkhani, & Taleizadeh. et al (2020), [12] studied an environmental impact and imperfect item model for a coordinated two-level international supply chain using an EOQ. Wahab, M. I. M., Mamun, S. M. H., & Ongkunaruk, P. et al. (2011), [13] addressed a combined economic lot size model with pricing and demand that is ecologically conscious. Zaroni, S., Mazzoldi, L., Zavanella, L. E., & Jaber, M. Y. et al. (2014), [14] discussed a Single- and batch-service queueing system with two servers. Sridhar, A., & Pitchai, R. A. et al. (2014), [15] developed a sustainable deterministic inventory model using a free distribution strategy to account for changing transportation costs. Mr. Karthic Mohan, Dr A Sridhar, & Dr B Malleeswaran et al. (2023), [16] developed a Fuzzy Inventory Model by Using Pentagonal Fuzzy Numbers, Mr. M. Karthic & Dr. A. Sridhar, et al. (2024).

2.1 Objectives:

1. This study aims to minimize surplus inventory levels while preserving operating efficiency, satisfying customer demands, and cutting related costs.
2. Inventory management and sustainability are now crucial aspects of management that are utilized to guarantee the productivity and profitability of many sectors.
3. Our study presents a system for an integrated inventory that prioritizes articles about the long-term viability of cost minimization. There are two types of cost reduction in this framework: setup and purchasing cost reduction.

3. Notations and Assumptions:

3.1 Decision Variables:

κ Safety element

Q Order quantity

L Lead time

s Setup cost (\$)

K Order cost (\$)

n Number of items to be delivered.

3.2 Parameters:

3.2.1 Vendor's side:

M_c Manufacturing cost (\$)

K_0 Setup cost (Initial) (\$)

h_c^v maintenance expenses (Vendor) (\$)

3.2.2. Buyer's side:

ω Reorder units

γ_c Backlog cost (\$)

D Demand (units)

P Production (units)

K_0 Order cost (Initial)(\$)

E_b Purchase cost (\$/unit) $E_v > E_b$

h_c^b maintenance expenses (Buyer) (\$)

3.3 Presumptions:

1. We addressed the utilization of SM-MR for environmental and In this scenario, green customer demand for consumers with instantaneous purchasing decreased expenses
2. Production and rework rates will always be in high demand.
3. The green and environmental factors influence market demand, which takes the following form.

$$\hat{\delta}k_{\alpha} = \sum_{k_{\alpha}}^{\xi} \delta k_{\alpha} \text{ where, } \delta k_{\alpha} = \hat{\delta}k_{\alpha}(\epsilon_m, \gamma_l) = \hat{\pi}(\gamma_l^c \gamma_l + \epsilon_m \epsilon_{\alpha}) \tag{1}$$

where the decision factors are the environment measure (ϵ_m) and the greening level (γ_l).

4. In order to lower the purchasing cost for a sustainable integrated SM-MR inventory model, the suggested model makes use of this discrete investment concept. In this fashion, we can define the model's discrete purchasing cost decrease as,

$$K_p = K_o \epsilon^{-pK_i} \tag{2}$$

5. The cost of a green investment each year is $GI_c = G_l g_l^2$, where g_l is the degree of greening improvement.

3.4 Mathematical Inventory model:

Inventory model can be formulated as follows

Total cost = Ordering cost + Holding cost + Varying transportation cost

$$TC = \frac{Dk_1}{mQ_0} + \frac{(m-1)h_1Q_1^2}{2Q_0} \left(\frac{P}{P-D} \right) + FQ_0 \tag{3}$$

Since $Q_1 = \frac{s_2Q_0}{h_2 + s_2}$, then $TC = \frac{Dk_1}{mQ_0} + \frac{(m-1)h_1 \left(\frac{s_2Q_0}{h_2 + s_2} \right)^2}{2Q_0} \left(\frac{P}{P-D} \right) + FQ_0$

$$TC = \frac{Dk_1}{mQ_0} + \frac{(m-1)h_1s_2^2Q_0}{2(h_2 + s_2)^2} \left(\frac{P}{P-D} \right) + FQ_0 \tag{4}$$

Differentiate w.r.to Q_0 , then

$$\frac{d}{dQ_0}(TC) = \frac{-Dk_1}{mQ_0^2} + \frac{(m-1)h_1s_2^2}{2(h_2 + s_2)^2} \left(\frac{P}{P-D} \right) + F$$

Again differentiate w.r.to Q_0 , then

$$\frac{d^2}{dQ_0^2}(TC) = \frac{2Dk_1}{mQ_0^3}, \text{ and } \frac{d^2}{dQ_0^2}(TC) > 0$$

If $\frac{d}{dQ_0}(TC) = 0$, then $\frac{-Dk_1}{mQ_0^2} + \frac{(m-1)h_1s_2^2}{2(h_2 + s_2)^2} \left(\frac{P}{P-D} \right) + F = 0$

$$\frac{(m-1)h_1s_2^2}{2(h_2 + s_2)^2} \left(\frac{P}{P-D} \right) + F = \frac{Dk_1}{mQ_0^2} \tag{5}$$

Hence the optimum inventory order quantity is

$$Q_0 = \sqrt{\frac{2Dk_1(h_2 + s_2)^2}{m(m-1)h_1s_2^2 \left(\frac{P}{P-D} \right) + 2mF(h_2 + s_2)^2}} \tag{6}$$

3.4 Integrated Inventory Model for Fuzzy Production Quantity:

Suppose fuzzy production quantity $\tilde{Q}_0$ be a pentagonal fuzzy number $\tilde{Q}_0 = (Q_{01}, Q_{02}, Q_{03}, Q_{04}, Q_{05})$ with

$$0 < Q_{01} \leq Q_{02} \leq Q_{03} \leq Q_{04} \leq Q_{05}$$

This gives us the approximate total manufacturing inventory cost.

$$TC = \frac{1}{8} \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{D_1 k_1}{m Q_{05}} + \frac{(m-1) h_1 s_2^2 Q_{01}}{2(h_2 + s_2)^2} \left(\frac{P}{P - D_5} \right) + 2m Q_{01} F_1 (h_2 + s_2)^2 + \right. \\ & 2 \left(\frac{D_2 k_1}{m Q_{04}} + \frac{(m-1) h_1 s_2^2 Q_{02}}{2(h_2 + s_2)^2} \left(\frac{P}{P - D_4} \right) + 2m Q_{02} F_2 (h_2 + s_2)^2 \right) + \\ & 2 \left(\frac{D_3 k_1}{m Q_{03}} + \frac{(m-1) h_1 s_2^2 Q_{03}}{2(h_2 + s_2)^2} \left(\frac{P}{P - D_3} \right) + 2m Q_{03} F_3 (h_2 + s_2)^2 \right) + \\ & 2 \left(\frac{D_4 k_1}{m Q_{02}} + \frac{(m-1) h_1 s_2^2 Q_{04}}{2(h_2 + s_2)^2} \left(\frac{P}{P - D_2} \right) + 2m Q_{04} F_4 (h_2 + s_2)^2 \right) + \\ & \left. \frac{D_5 k_1}{m Q_{01}} + \frac{(m-1) h_1 s_2^2 Q_{05}}{2(h_2 + s_2)^2} \left(\frac{P}{P - D_1} \right) + 2m Q_{05} F_5 (h_2 + s_2)^2 \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

We obtain the signed distance to get TC with $0 < Q_{01} \leq Q_{02} \leq Q_{03} \leq Q_{04} \leq Q_{05}$.

If will not change the meaning of above formula if we replace inequality conditions $0 < Q_{01} \leq Q_{02} \leq Q_{03} \leq Q_{04} \leq Q_{05}$ into the following inequality $Q_{02} - Q_{01} \geq 0, Q_{03} - Q_{02} \geq 0, Q_{04} - Q_{03} \geq 0, Q_{05} - Q_{04} \geq 0, Q_{01} > 0$.

4. Characterization of the Model:

The transportation cost inventory model is an essential component of supply chain management. It seeks to maximize the ratio of transportation expenses to inventory maintenance expenses. In this piece, we'll go over the essential elements of the transportation cost inventory model and examine how it affects organizations.

Figure 1: Manufacture and Maintenance Level

4.1 Manufacturer's Cost:

Setup Cost $\mathcal{G}$ maintenance expenses

Setup cost: Every cycle, the manufacturer has to set up once for production and rework for new items. Cycle C_T 's initial reworking batch is,

$$sC_m = \frac{\hat{R}_c^r + \hat{R}_c^p}{C_T} \quad (8)$$

maintenance expenses: The manufacturer creates m batches of new goods of size $\hat{C}_{rw}$ & after reworking n batches of things of size $\hat{C}_{pr}$. (Refer fig 1)

$$HC_m^1 = \frac{\hat{M}_h^c}{2T} \left\{ \frac{m \hat{C}_r^2}{\hat{D}_c^r} + \frac{n \hat{C}_p^2}{\hat{E}_c^n} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Figure 2: Items recovered for a single manufacturer and many retailers.

maintenance expenses of recovered items to be used for reworking which is given by,

$$HC_m^2 = \frac{m\bar{D}_h^c \hat{C}_r (\bar{D}_c^r - \epsilon_r \delta k)}{2\bar{D}_c^r} \tag{10}$$

Purchasing Expenses: For every cycle of $(m_p + n_p)$ cohorts, the k^{th} merchant's purchase price is as follows:

$$K_c = \hat{C}_t = (m_p + n_p) \frac{C_p}{C_T} \tag{11}$$

Maintenance expenses: From the area under the curve, which is made up of one triangle and $(m + n - 1)$ trapezoids, the maintenance expenses per unit time for the k^{th} merchant may be found as follows. (Refer fig 2)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Area} = & \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{1}{2} \{J_{ar}^k + J_{br}^{k+1}\} y_r + \text{area of } m^{th} \text{ trapezoid} + \text{area of triangle} \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \{J_{ap}^k + J_{bp}^{k+1}\} y_p \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where, $y_r = \frac{\hat{C}_r}{\delta c^r}$ and $y_p = \frac{\hat{C}_p}{\hat{E}_c^n}$ and

$$\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{1}{2} \{J_{ar}^k + J_{br}^{k+1}\} y_r = \frac{m(m-1)\hat{C}_r^2}{2\delta_k \delta c^r} - \frac{m(m-1)\hat{C}_r^2 \delta k}{\delta c^r} + \frac{m\hat{C}_r^2 \delta k}{2D_c^r} \tag{13}$$

Therefore, the Area of m^{th} trapezoid is,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{m\hat{C}_r \hat{C}_p \delta k}{\hat{E}_c^n} - \frac{(m-1)\hat{C}_r \hat{C}_p \delta k}{\delta^r \hat{E}_c^n} - \frac{\hat{C}_p^2 \delta k}{2(\delta c^n)^2} \\ \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \{J_{ap}^k + J_{bp}^{k+1}\} y_p = & (n-1) \left\{ \frac{m\hat{C}_r \hat{C}_p \delta k}{\hat{E}_c^n} - (m-1) \frac{\hat{C}_r \hat{C}_p \delta k}{\hat{D}_c^r \hat{E}_c^n} + \frac{\delta k \hat{C}_p^2}{\hat{E}_c^n} \right\} \\ & + \frac{n(n-1)\hat{C}_p^2}{2\delta k \hat{E}_c^n} - \frac{n(n-1)\hat{C}_p^2 \delta k}{2D_c^r} + \frac{(n-1)\hat{C}_p^2 \delta k}{2\hat{E}_c^n} \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Area of the triangle is,

$$\frac{1}{2\delta k} \left\{ (m\hat{C}_r \delta k) - \frac{(m-1)C_p \delta k}{\hat{D}_c^r} + n\hat{C}_p \left(1 - \frac{\delta k}{\hat{E}_c^n} \right) \right\}^2$$

After some simplifications in (6) then we get,

$$HC_r = \sum_{k=1}^{\xi} \left\{ \frac{\hat{A}_k \epsilon_r (m+n) \delta k}{m\hat{C}_r} + H_k \delta k \hat{C}_r \left(\frac{l}{2\epsilon_r \delta k} - \frac{(\epsilon_r - 2)(1-l)}{2\bar{D}_c^r} - \frac{(k+1)l(1-\epsilon_r)^k}{2n\epsilon_r \hat{E}_c^n} \right) \right\} \tag{15}$$

$$EC = \frac{\delta k e_1}{m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p} + \kappa \delta k \left(I_f^c + \delta(1 - I_f^c) \right) + \left[e_2 + \alpha_1 \alpha_2 E_c^d \left(\frac{\delta k^2 I_f^{c^2}}{2} m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p \right) \right] \tag{16}$$

The following relationships and formulas can be used to get the total cost function,

$$T = \frac{m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p}{\delta k}; m\hat{C}_r = \epsilon_r \delta k T; n\hat{C}_p = (1 - \epsilon_r) \delta k T = m\hat{C}_r \frac{(1 - \epsilon_r)}{\epsilon_r}$$

By using (7), (8), (9), (10), (11), (15) and (16) we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \hat{C}_p, \hat{C}_r) &= GIC + SC_m + HC_m^1 + HC_m^2 + HC_r + OC_r + EC \\ &\text{where, } \widehat{TC} - \text{SM-MR system's total estimated cost.} \\ \widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \hat{C}_p, \hat{C}_r) &= \frac{(R_c^r + R_c^p)\delta k \epsilon_r}{m\hat{C}_r} + \frac{\hat{M}_h^c \delta k \hat{C}_r}{2} \left\{ \frac{\epsilon_r}{\hat{D}_c^r} + \frac{m(1-\epsilon_r)^2}{n\epsilon_r \hat{E}_c^n} \right\} + \frac{m\hat{D}_h^c \hat{C}_r (\hat{D}_c^r - \epsilon_r \delta k)}{2\hat{D}_c^r} \\ &\quad + \sum_{k=1}^{\xi} \left\{ \frac{\hat{A}_k \epsilon_r (m+n) \delta k}{m\hat{C}_r} + H_k \delta k \hat{C}_r \left(\frac{l}{2\epsilon_r \delta k} - \frac{(\epsilon_r - 2)(1-l)}{2\hat{D}_c^r} - \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{(k+1)l(1-\epsilon_r)^k}{2n\epsilon_r \hat{E}_c^n} \right) \right\} + G_l g_l^2 + \frac{\delta k e_1}{m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p} + \kappa \delta k \left(I_f^c + \delta(1 - I_f^c) \right) \\ &\quad + \left[e_2 + \alpha_1 \alpha_2 E_c^d \left(\frac{\delta k I_f^c}{2} (m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p) \right) \right] \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Diff. w.r.to g_l ,

$$\frac{\partial \widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \hat{C}_p, \hat{C}_r)}{\partial g_l} = g_l(y_1) - (y_2 + y_3 + y_4) - e_2 + \frac{\epsilon_r \hat{\pi} g_l^c (R_c^r + R_c^p)}{m\hat{C}_r} \tag{18}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 &= \left[2G_l + \alpha_1 \alpha_2 E_c^d \left((\hat{\pi} g_l^c I_f^c)^2 (m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p) \right) \right] \\ y_2 &= \hat{\pi} \hat{M}_h^c \hat{C}_r g_l^c \left\{ \frac{\epsilon_r}{\hat{D}_c^r} + \frac{m(1-\epsilon_r)^2}{n\epsilon_r \hat{E}_c^n} - \frac{m\epsilon_r \hat{D}_h^c \hat{C}_r}{2\hat{D}_c^r} \right\} \\ y_3 &= \sum_{k=1}^{\xi} \left\{ \frac{\hat{A}_k \epsilon_r (m+n) \hat{\pi} g_l^c \epsilon_r}{m\hat{C}_r} + H_k \hat{C}_r \left(\frac{l}{k\epsilon_r} + \frac{(\epsilon_r - 2k)(1-l) g_l^c \hat{\pi}}{2\hat{D}_c^r} - \frac{(k+1)l(1-\epsilon_r)^k \hat{\pi} g_l^c}{2n\epsilon_r \hat{E}_c^n} \right) \right\} \\ y_4 &= \frac{g_l^c \hat{\pi} e_1}{m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p} + \kappa g_l^c \hat{\pi} \left(I_f^c + \delta(1 - I_f^c) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Diff. w.r.to g_l ,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \hat{C}_p, \hat{C}_r)}{\partial g_l^2} = y_1 - (y_2 + y_3 + y_4) - e_2 + \frac{\epsilon_r \hat{\pi} g_l^c (R_c^r + R_c^p)}{m\hat{C}_r} > 0 \tag{19}$$

To get the greening improvement level (g_l) that equals zero through

$$g_l = \frac{(y_2 + y_3 + y_4) - e_2 + \frac{\epsilon_r \hat{\pi} g_l^c (R_c^r + R_c^p)}{m\hat{C}_r}}{y_1} \tag{20}$$

Diff. w.r.to e_m ,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \hat{C}_p, \hat{C}_r)}{\partial e_m} &= \frac{-\epsilon_r \hat{\pi} e_m (R_c^r + R_c^p)}{m\hat{C}_r} + \frac{e_a}{g_l^c} [y_2 + y_3] + y_5 \\ &\quad + \alpha_1 \alpha_2 E_c^d \{ \hat{\pi} e_a e_m I_f^{c2} (m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p) \} \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

where, $y_5 = \hat{\pi} e_a \left[\frac{e_1}{(m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p)} + \kappa \left(I_f^c + \delta(1 - I_f^c) \right) \right]$

Diff. w.r.to e_m ,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \hat{C}_p, \hat{C}_r)}{\partial e_m^2} = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 E_c^d \{ \hat{\pi} e_a I_f^{c2} (m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p) \} > 0 \tag{22}$$

In order to get the environmental performance measure (e_m) that equating to zero will be,

$$e_m = \frac{\frac{\epsilon_r \hat{\pi} (R_c^r + R_c^p)}{m\hat{C}_r} + \frac{e_a}{g_l^c} [y_2 + y_3] + y_5}{\alpha_1 \alpha_2 E_c^d \{ \hat{\pi} e_a I_f^{c2} (m\hat{C}_r + n\hat{C}_p) \}} \tag{23}$$

Diff. w.r.to $\hat{Q}_r$,

$$\frac{\partial \widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \hat{C}_p, \hat{C}_r)}{\partial \hat{Q}_r} = \frac{-\hat{D}_k}{m\hat{Q}_r^2} [y_3 + e_1] + \sum_{k=1}^{\xi} H_k \hat{D}_k (y_1) + y_2 \tag{24}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 &= \left[\frac{l}{2\epsilon_r \delta k} - \frac{(\epsilon_r - 2k)(1-l)}{2\hat{D}_c^r} - \frac{(k+1)l(\epsilon_r - 1)^k}{2n\epsilon_r \hat{E}_c^n} \right] \\ y_2 &= \frac{\hat{M}_h^c \delta k}{2} \left\{ \frac{\epsilon_r}{\hat{D}_c^r} + \frac{m(1-\epsilon_r)^2}{n\epsilon_r \hat{E}_c^n} \right\} + \frac{m\hat{D}_h^c \hat{C}_r (\hat{D}_c^r - \epsilon_r \delta k)}{2\hat{D}_c^r} + \left[m\alpha_1 \alpha_2 E_c^d \left(\frac{\delta k^2 I_f^{c2}}{2} \right) \right] \\ y_3 &= (R_c^r + R_c^p) \epsilon_r + \sum_{k=1}^{\xi} \{ \hat{A}_k \epsilon_r (m+n) \} \end{aligned}$$

Diff. w.r.to $\hat{Q}_r$,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \widehat{C}_p, \widehat{C}_r)}{\partial \widehat{Q}_r^2} = \frac{2\widehat{D}_k}{m\widehat{Q}_r^3} [y_3 + e_1] > 0$$

To determine the rework lot-size ($\widehat{Q}_r$),

$$\widehat{C}_r = \sqrt{\frac{\widehat{D}_k(y_3 + e_1)}{m \sum_{k=1}^{\xi} H_k \widehat{D}_k(y_1) + y_2}} \tag{25}$$

By utilizing the relations, productivity lot-size ($\widehat{Q}_p$) can be obtained,

$$\widehat{C}_p = \frac{m\widehat{Q}_r}{n} \left(\frac{1 - \epsilon_r}{\epsilon_r} \right) \tag{26}$$

5. Quantitative Representation:

Example 5.1: The information used as intake for the specified characteristics of case (5.1) is shown in Table (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5) provide the best possible results for the SMMR model at the lowest possible cost. In this case, † represents the optimal productivity $\mathcal{G}$ period of correction (n, m) and order quantities ($\widehat{C}_p, \widehat{C}_r$), ecological measure (e_m), greening investment level (g_l), and minimal total expected cost ($\widehat{TC}$), in that order.

Table 1: Input parameters and its numeric amounts

Parameters	values	Parameters	values
$\widehat{E}_c^n$	780	h_1	4.8
$\widehat{K}_c^p$	45	h_2	9.5
$\widehat{M}_h^c$	14	h_3	14.5
$\widehat{D}_h^c$	7.9	h_4	19
$\widehat{K}_c^r$	99	G_l	23
$\widehat{D}_c^r$	725	e_a	0.321
g_l^c	1.25	$p > 0$	0.09
A_i	0.45	A_o	990
α_1	0.1	α_2	0.001
I_f^c	0.001	δ	0.5
E_c^d	10	κ	2.5
ϵ_r	0.010	$\widehat{\pi}$	900
e_1	12	e_2	1.8

Table 2: Ideal outcomes for $\widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \widehat{C}_p, \widehat{C}_r)$ w.r.to k^{th} Retailer, where $k = 1$

n	m	$\widehat{\delta k}$	$\widehat{A}_k$	g_l	e_m	$\widehat{C}_r$	$\widehat{C}_p$	$(\widehat{TC})$
1	3.5	97.31	811.12	0.0386	0.0189	1.271	379.611	3584.12
2	7.5	91.97	601.35	0.0129	0.0067	0.681	237.811	4192.15
3	3.5	58.55	686.45	0.0282	0.0191	1.181	115.581	2108.19
4	5.5	170.20	444.86	0.3886	0.0227	3.441	424.171	2638.17
5	5.5	16.26	217.96	0.6550	0.1512	0.773	76.695	2526.18
6	8	23.92	343.47	0.0211	0.0089	0.30	38.562	1179.931[†]
7	3.5	44.60	616.87	0.0279	0.0156	1.221	51.012	2037.18

8	1.5	66.31	666.42	0.0238	0.0058	4.183	51.811	2856.41
9	1.5	65.38	677.57	0.0231	0.0156	4.365	47.912	2986.81
10	1.4	66.42	689.65	0.0211	0.0278	4.312	46.551	2988.01

Table 3: Ideal outcomes for $\widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \widehat{C}_p, \widehat{C}_r)$ w.r.to k^{th} Retailer, where $k = 2$

n	m	$\widehat{\delta k}$	$\widehat{A}_k$	g_l	e_m	$\widehat{C}_r$	$\widehat{C}_p$	$(\widehat{TC})$
i	5	85.23	899.23	1.0234	0.1234	1.01	299.12	2999.9
ii	5	55.53	612.56	1.0123	0.1103	1.02	111.12	2222.2
iii	4	23.34	752.27	0.5531	0.0886	0.44	40.01	1120.9
iv	4	51.78	640.34	0.0243	0.0077	1.13	84.45	2037.1
v	4	65.16	815.46	0.0284	0.0064	2.11	83.63	2795.4

Table 4: Ideal outcomes for $\widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \widehat{C}_p, \widehat{C}_r)$ w.r.to k^{th} Retailer, where $k = 3$

n	m	$\widehat{\delta k}$	$\widehat{A}_k$	g_l	e_m	$\widehat{C}_r$	$\widehat{C}_p$	$(\widehat{TC})$
i	3	88.12	1392	1.0861	1.0251	1.78	314.12	4967.7
ii	3	92.56	1264.7	1.1166	1.1154	1.68	137.23	4301.9
iii	3	33.31	499.33	1.0448	1.0225	1.66	44.43	1750.9
iv	2	73.54	1237.8	0.0753	0.0140	2.79	68.46	4303.0
v	2	75.59	1288.5	0.0688	0.1145	2.98	60.66	4763.0

Table 5: Ideal outcomes for $\widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \widehat{C}_p, \widehat{C}_r)$ w.r.to k^{th} Retailer, where $k = 4$

n	m	$\widehat{\delta k}$	$\widehat{A}_k$	g_l	e_m	$\widehat{C}_r$	$\widehat{C}_p$	$(\widehat{TC})$
i	4	95.11	988.22	1.1470	1.0190	2.33	383.35	3969.8
ii	5	58.45	688.89	1.1290	1.0199	1.85	158.25	2953.8
iii	3	59.29	700.34	0.1294	0.0199	1.88	69.12	2401.01
iv	3	55.26	698.96	0.1270	0.0188	1.72	59.23	2554.4
v	3	53.73	700.98	0.1248	0.0185	1.88	58.82	2751.7

Example 5.2: The information used as intake for the specified characteristics of case (5.2) is shown in Table (6), (7), (8), (9), and (10) provide the best possible results for the SM-MR model at the lowest possible cost. In this case, † represents the optimal productivity & 3 period of correction (n, m) and order quantities ($\widehat{C}_p, \widehat{C}_r$), ecological measure (e_m), greening investment level (g_l), and minimal total expected cost ($\widehat{TC}$), in that order.

Table 6: Input parameters and its numeric amounts

Parameters	values	parameters	values
$\hat{E}_c^n$	1010	h_5	4.5
$\hat{K}_c^p$	33	h_6	6.5
$\hat{M}_h^c$	28	h_7	8.5
$\hat{D}_h^c$	18	h_8	12.5
$\hat{K}_c^r$	160	G_l	21
$\hat{D}_c^r$	550	e_a	0.15
g_l^f	1.2	$p > 0$	0.55
A_i	0.3	A_o	1500
α_1	0.4	α_2	0.10
I_f^c	0.6	δ	0.55
E_c^d	5.5	κ	2.5
ϵ_r	0.12	$\hat{\pi}$	850
e_1	5.5	e_2	2.55

Table 7: Ideal outcomes for $\widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \hat{C}_p, \hat{C}_r)$ w.r.to k^{th} Retailer, where $k = 5$

n	m	δk	$\hat{A}_k$	g_l	e_m	$\hat{C}_r$	$\hat{C}_p$	$(\widehat{TC})$
i	3	89.20	535.78	0.1171	0.1346	4.96	204.26	1585.1
ii	3	36.69	449.97	0.1154	0.1138	2.22	47.73	1041.01[†]
iii	3	265.55	1125.8	0.1655	0.1180	5.82	285.98	10333
iv	3	274.53	1171.1	0.1506	0.1149	6.51	200.01	12315
v	3	284.26	1153.3	0.1153	0.1214	6.86	215.21	12143

Table 8: Ideal outcomes for $\widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \hat{C}_p, \hat{C}_r)$ w.r.to k^{th} Retailer, where $k = 6$

n	m	δk	$\hat{A}_k$	g_l	e_m	$\hat{C}_r$	$\hat{C}_p$	$(\widehat{TC})$
i	2	88.79	521.12	1.2284	1.1528	4.13	167.98	1736.5
ii	2	37.76	467.78	0.1185	0.1100	1.88	43.34	1260.01[†]
iii	2	58.19	488.05	0.1946	0.1482	4.07	79.17	1377.2
iv	2	58.51	494.55	0.1787	0.1457	4.14	56.37	1391.6

Table 9: Ideal outcomes for $\widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \widehat{C}_p, \widehat{C}_r)$ w.r.to k^{th} Retailer, where $k = 7$

n	m	δk	$\widehat{A}_k$	g_l	e_m	$\widehat{C}_r$	$\widehat{C}_p$	$(\widehat{TC})$
i	2	88.69	626.26	1.1537	1.0593	4.69	169.32	1968.7
ii	2	58.12	485.23	1.1156	1.1155	3.30	69.98	1410.9
iii	2	58.27	485.69	0.0898	0.0626	3.87	49.82	1534.7
iv	2	47.22	493.26	0.0822	0.0552	2.6032	43.28	1572.7

Table 10: Ideal outcomes for $\widehat{TC}(m, n, g_l, e_m, \widehat{C}_p, \widehat{C}_r)$ w.r.to k^{th} Retailer, where $k = 8$

n	m	δk	$\widehat{A}_k$	g_l	e_m	$\widehat{C}_r$	$\widehat{C}_p$	$(\widehat{TC})$
1	3	89.11	859.73	0.1700	0.1530	2.96	195.73	2920.41
2	2	56.62	515.59	0.1101	0.1666	2.66	62.22	1683.91
3	2	50.59	495.76	0.1913	0.1751	2.60	42.84	1704.12
4	3	41.47	558.39	0.1873	0.1639	1.55	38.43	1880.10

5.1 Managerial Insights:

This section provides an overview of the suggested model's management implications, based on the numerical examples (5.1) and (5.2). where, for Ex.(5.1), $k = 1,2,3,4$ retailers and for Ex. (5.2), $k = 5,6,7,8$ retailers.

Example (5.1):

(a) We conserve the minimal amount of money through (2), as $\widehat{TC} = 1179.931$ at productivity & period of correction by applying quantity measurements $l = 6, k = 8$ is $\widehat{C}_p = 41.123$ & $\widehat{C}_r = 0.30$, degree of greening $g_l = 0.0211$ & ecological assesses $e_m = 0.0089$.

(b) We conserve the minimal amount of money through (3), as $\widehat{TC} = 1120.9$ at productivity & period of correction by applying quantity measurements $l = 3, k = 4$ is $\widehat{C}_p = 39.99$ & $\widehat{C}_r = 0.44$, degree of greening $g_l = 0.5531$ & **ecological** assesses $e_m = 0.0886$.

(c) We conserve the minimal amount of money through (4), as $\widehat{TC} = 1750.9$ at productivity & period of correction by applying quantity measurements $l = 3, k = 3$ is $\widehat{C}_p = 44.43$ & $\widehat{C}_r = 0.66$, degree of greening $g_l = 0.0448$ & ecological assesses $e_m = 0.0225$.

(d) We conserve the minimal amount of money through (5), as $\widehat{TC} = 2401.01$ at productivity & period of correction by applying quantity measurements $l = 4, k = 3$ is $\widehat{C}_p = 69.23$ & $\widehat{C}_r = 0.88$, degree of greening $g_l = 1.1294$ & ecological assesses $e_m = 0.0199$.

Example (5.2):

(a) We conserve the minimal amount of money through (7), as $\widehat{TC} = 1041.01$ at productivity & period of correction by applying quantity measurements $l = 2, k = 3$ is $\widehat{C}_p = 47.73$ & $\widehat{C}_r = 2.22$, degree of greening $g_l = 0.1154$ & ecological assess $e_m = 0.1138$.

(b) We conserve the minimal amount of money through (8), as $\widehat{TC} = 1260.01$ at productivity & period of correction by applying quantity measurements $l = 2, k = 2$ is $\widehat{C}_p = 43.34$ & $\widehat{C}_r = 1.88$, degree of greening $g_l = 0.1185$ & ecological assess $e_m = 0.1100$.

(c) We conserve the minimal amount of money through 9, as $\widehat{TC} = 1410.9$ at productivity & period of correction by applying quantity measurements $l = 2, k = 2$ is $\widehat{C}_p = 69.98$ & $\widehat{C}_r = 3.30$, degree of greening $g_l = 0.1156$ & ecological assess $e_m = 0.1155$.

(d) We conserve the minimal amount of money through 10 , as $\widehat{TC} = 1683.91$ at productivity & period of correction by applying quantity measurements $l = 2, k = 2$ is $\widehat{C}_p = 62.22$ & $\widehat{C}_r = 2.66$, degree of greening $g_l = 0.1101$ & ecological assesse $e_m = 0.1666$.

Table (11) represents the eight merchants' ideal outcomes in the SM-MR model, and ‡ denotes the first three optimal minimal SC costs in the model.

Table 11: Comparisons of ideal outcomes

No. of retailers	n	m	$\widehat{\delta k}$	$\widehat{A}_k$	g_l	e_m	$\widehat{C}_r$	$\widehat{C}_p$	$(\widehat{TC})$
$k = 1$	6	8	23.89	345.47	0.0151	0.0098	0.32	39.56	1185.3 ‡
$k = 2$	3	3	23.24	752.07	0.5931	0.0817	0.49	40.10	1111.4 ‡
$k = 3$	3	2	32.71	513.28	0.0478	0.1195	0.65	42.53	1752.1
$k = 4$	4	2	54.29	698.34	0.0254	0.0199	1.56	68.26	2411.9
$k = 5$	2	2	35.42	441.30	0.0653	0.0358	1.89	47.13	1038.5 ‡
$k = 6$	4	2	37.36	468.99	0.0695	0.0401	1.73	42.32	1261.7
$k = 7$	2	1	55.14	479.74	0.1956	0.1555	2.79	68.56	1399.2
$k = 8$	2	1	57.20	504.62	0.1131	0.1326	2.12	60.46	1662.1
$k = 9$	3	2	55.20	504.49	0.1101	0.0676	2.58	60.92	1692.3
$k = 10$	3	2	58.20	505.59	0.1121	0.0686	2.56	60.85	1665.2

6. Conclusion:

We looked at the importance of green and ecologically conscious demand in production scenarios in this section, as well as the necessity of updating inventory models. We make expenditures to reduce the retailer's purchasing costs; the manufacturer's joint total optimal cost is effectively obtained through the discrete purchasing cost reduction and CEs. Furthermore, we discovered that manufacturers and merchants can improve the ecological sustainability of their products, boost profit margins, and cut prices overall by putting discrete purchasing cost reduction tactics into practice. This section's numerical responses and management insights indicate that our strategy is more appropriate for both cost minimization and profit maximization.

References:

- [1] Villena, V. H., & Gioia, D. A. (2020). A more sustainable supply chain. *Harvard Business Review*, 98(2), 84-93.
- [2] Barbosa-Povoa, A. P., da Silva, C., & Carvalho, A. (2018). Opportunities and challenges in sustainable supply chain: An operations research perspective. *European journal of operational research*, 268(2), 399-431.
- [3] Bjerketvedt, V. S., Tomasgard, A., & Roussanaly, S. (2020). Optimal design and cost of ship-based CO2 transport under uncertainties and fluctuations. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 103, 103190.
- [4] Yadav, A. S., & Swami, A. (2019). A volume flexible two-warehouse model with fluctuating demand and holding cost under inflation. *International Journal of Procurement Management*, 12(4), 441-456.
- [5] Jones, J. (2022). The winners, losers and shapers of fluctuating fuel prices in Sierra Leone. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 71, 54-63.

- [6] B. Malleeswaran & R. Uthayakumar (2023) A single-manufacturer multi-retailer sustainable reworking model for green and environmental sensitive demand under discrete ordering cost reduction, *Journal of Management Analytics*, 10:1, 109-128, DOI: 10.1080/23270012.2022.2030255
- [7] Malleeswaran, B., & Uthayakumar, R. (2020). An integrated vendor-buyer supply chain model for backorder price discount and price-dependent demand using service level constraints and carbon emission cost. *International Journal of Systems Science: Operations & Logistics*, 1-10. doi:10.1080/23302674.2020.1833258
- [8] B. Malleeswaran & R. Uthayakumar (2021) Consignment stock management for reducing waste items and GHG emissions using remanufacturing, emission penalties and promotional efforts under capacity constraints, *International Journal of Sustainable Engineering*, 14:6, 1538-1550, doi:10.1080/19397038.2021.1964632
- [9] Saha, S., & Goyal, S. K. (2015). Supply chain coordination contracts with inventory level and retail price dependent demand. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 161, 140-152.doi:10.1016/j.ijpe.2014.12.025
- [10] Srivastava, S. K. (2007). Green supply-chain management: a state-of-the-art literature review. *International journal of management reviews*, 9(1), 53-80. doi:10.1111/j.1468-2370.2007.00202.x
- [11] Taleizadeh, A. A., Hazarkhani, B., & Moon, I. (2020). Joint pricing and inventory decisions with carbon emission considerations, partial backordering and planned discounts. *Annals of Operations Research*, 290(1), 95-113.doi:10.1007/s10479-018-2968-y
- [12] Wahab, M. I. M., Mamun, S. M. H., & Ongkunaruk, P. (2011). EOQ models for a coordinated two-level international supply chain considering imperfect items and environmental impact. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 134(1), 151-158. doi:10.1016/j.ijpe.2011.06.008
- [13] Zanoni, S., Mazzoldi, L., Zavanella, L. E., & Jaber, M. Y. (2014). A joint economic lot size model with price and environmentally sensitive demand. *Production & Manufacturing Research*, 2(1), 341-354. doi:10.1080/21693277.2014.913125
- [14] Sridhar, A., & Pitchai, R. A. (2014). Two Server Queueing System with Single and Batch Service. *International Journal of Applied*, 4(2), 15-26.
- [15] Mr Karthic Mohan, Dr A Sridhar, & Dr B Malleeswaran, "A Sustainable Deterministic Inventory Model for Varying Transportation Cost with Free Distribution Approach", *IJRAR - International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, E-ISSN 2348-1269, P-ISSN 2349-5138, Volume.10, Issue 3, Page No pp.568-573, September 2023, doi.one/10.1729/Journal.36933.
- [16] Mr. M. Karthic & Dr. A. Sridhar, "A Fuzzy Inventory Model Using Pentagonal Fuzzy Numbers", *Tuijin Jishu/Journal of Propulsion Technology*, ISSN: 1001-4055, Vol.45, No.1, Page No: 2646-2659, (2024).